

Title: The sociological and technological implications of the BDE explosion

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The sociological and technological implications of the big data explosion (BDE) have left many corporate professionals blindsided, and faced with a management dilemma. In order to counteract this blindsided dilemma, change management, knowledge management and identity management are focus areas that can facilitate a full paradigm shift towards leveraging data and technology more effectively within organizations.

In law firms, for example, a tension exists with respect to traditional transactional work, as against work that is driven around data and technological innovations. The experiential content of this presentation and anecdotal references, pivot around the law firm context. The discussions and related experiences are, however, relevant for most if not all organizations, which at some point in time are invariably clients of a law firm. The discussions of this presentation, break the narrative around historical organizational structures, and explore how a layered spectrum of new age technological professionals can advance innovation, productivity and revenue within an organization.

The aforementioned new age group of technological professionals is a spectrum of fluid professional identities that straddle the silos of data, technology, sociology and education; data scientists, data engineers, database administrators – just to name a few relevant identities. As a result of this, technology is a breeding ground for fluidity and flexibility: where all of this revolves around the millennial (or Gen Y) generation, followed by anticipated attention to Centennials (or Gen Z/iGen), with more focus expected towards the other generational identifiers

that are emerging. Let's engage in this upcoming hour on all that is relevant for data (BDE), technology, sociology and the identity spectra of the differing generation categories.

BIOGRAPHY:

Roger Francis completed his doctorate at the University of Calgary (Education – Adult Learning). He also holds a master's in Education - Digital Technologies from the University of Ontario Institute of Technology. Roger's interests in the intersections of data, technology and adult learning led to his ACEDS and AIIM certifications in eDiscovery and information governance. In addition to research and writing within the intersections of identity/technology, and developing/teaching technology courses and seminars, Roger is also involved in law firm cross border (USA/CAN) e-Discovery projects and initiatives.

